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EURO-LABS

EUROpean Laboratories for Accelerator Based Science
HORIZON-INFRA-2021-SERV-01-07 Project EURO-LABS

DELIVERABLE REPORT

EURO-LABS Users' Final Diversity Report

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Abstract:

This document constitutes Deliverable D5.2 of the EURO-LABS project. It reports the status on diversity of the EURO-LABS user community. The Nuclear Physics and the High Energy Physics Accelerator and Detector communities have a proven track record on extensive and broad approach with respect to equality issues. Besides gender, these communities also embraces multicultural and multinational dimensions of equality. On this basis EURO-LABS has adopted a more pro-active policy. The result of these good practices are supported by the global EURO-LABS statistics presented in this diversity report, which cover the period from the beginning of the project on September 1st 2022, to October 31st 2025.

EURO-LABS Consortium, 2025

For more information on EURO-LABS, its partners and contributors please see <https://web.infn.it/EURO-LABS/>

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Delivery Slip

	Name	Partner	Date
Authored by	M.J.G. Borge Pablo F. López	CSIC/IEM CERN	27/11/2025
Edited by	M.J.G. Borge Pablo F. López Cloe Levointurier-Vajda	CSIC/IEM CERN CERN	10/12/2025
Reviewed by	M. J. G Borge [WP5 coordinator] Maria Colonna [Deputy Scientific coordinator]	CSIC/IEM INFN	12/12/2025
Approved by	A. Navin [Scientific coordinator]	GANIL	19/12/2025

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Executive summary

One of the aims of the EURO-LABS WP5.1 is to ensure large diversity, through a strong effort in engaging people of different nationality, gender, age, and level of professional expertise.

EURO-LABS reflects a very large and diverse community, adhering to the core principles of open access, diversity and equal opportunity. The Research Infrastructures (RI) in EURO-LABS are engaged in fostering equality, diversity and inclusion by incorporating these principles in the selection of the users sponsored by this Transnational Access program. Task Leaders and Facility Coordinators implement these general guidelines and in particular take care of gender equality, and diversity in the course of this project. This is monitored by the EURO-LABS Steering Committee and also as part of a task in WP5.

The statistics presented here do not take into account users if they have been supported more than once, leading to a sample of 2745 users. Aspects monitored and analysed in this report include geography, age and gender diversity.

The geographical diversity is enormous, showing the attractiveness of the European facilities covered by EURO-LABS worldwide. The 42 facilities involved in EURO-LABS welcomed users from institutions located in 54 countries, mainly from European Union. The users represent a wide range of nationalities, as they come from 85 countries, including developing countries. There is also an important number of users from US, Canada and Japan.

The gender distribution in the users' community is characterized by a large proportion of men (~73%). Nevertheless, the participation of women has grown since the first reporting period where was ~ 25%. It is important to point out that in the largest group of users, i.e., PhD students, corresponding to ages between 26 and 30 years old, the percentage of women is 31 %.

The age of the users has also been monitored and analysed. They are mainly composed by young people: the largest group corresponds to PhD students, followed closely by Post-docs (31-35 years old). Interestingly, and as curiosity has no age, we notice that more than 2 % of users are 70 years old or older.

1. INTRODUCTION

The diversity of people in research is recognized as an important factor in boosting productivity and innovation and encouraging under represented communities. The definition of *diversity* corresponds to the acknowledgement, respect, and appreciation of the fact that people differ in many ways, visible or invisible, mainly in age, gender and sexual orientation, national and ethnic origin, civil status and familial situation, religious convictions, political and philosophical opinions, and physical abilities. A diversity charter has been elaborated by APPEC, ECFA and NuPECC [1,2], specific to the research field covered by EURO-LABS, and it is endorsed at least in the main points by the corresponding research organisations, scientific collaborations including international advisory committees for conferences. Steps have already been taken towards achieving these goals. The RIs of EURO-LABS project follow such initiatives and monitor its application through a statistical analysis, as presented in this report.

The diversity and gender balance in the EURO-LABS community needs to mirror the European society. Its added value has been demonstrated in industry as well as in research, where most effects of gender and ethnic inclusions have been systematically followed. Diversity should also be considered in terms of scientific background, culture, and perspective. In addition, diversity also includes encouraging suggestions from younger physicists, as well as the expertise sharing of engineers, technicians and researchers. A vast range of technical competencies are also required to support research activities such as those in vacuum, ion beam production and acceleration, electronics, computing and instrumentation, etc.

The Nuclear Physics and High Energy Physics community of EURO-LABS have a proven track record on extensive and broad approach with respect to equality and diversity issues.

This pro-active policy has been adopted in EURO-LABS. In this direction actions have been reported in both the periods P1 and P2. The statistics of relevant parameters of diversity such as the user gender, nationality and age has been obtained through WP coordinators, Task Leaders and Facility Coordinators, and monitored by the EURO-LABS Steering Committee, and also as part of one of the tasks of WP5 (Open, Diverse and Inclusive Science).

EURO-LABS reflects a large and diverse community, adhering to the core principles of open access, diversity and equal opportunity. The Research Infrastructures (RI) in EURO-LABS are engaged in fostering equality, diversity and inclusion by stimulating to incorporate these principles in the selection of the users sponsored in the Transnational Access program. Task Leaders and Facility Coordinators follow these general guidelines and in particular take care of gender equality and diversity in the course of this project.

The dynamic integration of the diverse, but naturally linked, communities of this consortium leads to a better awareness of the expertise and working cultures, and thus to cross-fertilization, and can be seen as unity in diversity. This is important, as the ambition of the

EURO-LABS project is to create a pool of trained and well-informed researchers in the area of nuclear science and accelerator/detector science and technology.

2. MONITORING DIVERSITY

Monitoring provides a clear understanding of our current position and serves as a foundation for expanding diversity and strengthening inclusive practices. The exercise of monitoring is important in order to define diversity objectives and the associated actions.

As already mentioned, diversity includes many parameters. Among them, the promotion of gender equality is the most monitored one in Europe. The present report goes beyond monitoring gender also considering the age and the nationalities of the users, whether they are Europeans, from associated countries or from elsewhere in the world. We also analyzed their home institutions and the RIs where they go to do their research. Diversity of our users' age will also be presented.

2.1 STATISTICS

2.1.1 Methodology

This section presents the methodology adopted to showcase our users' diversity. The data collected are about users benefiting from EURO-LABS Transnational Access (TA) programme, between September 1st 2022 and October 31st 2025.

Since the beginning of the project, some users accessed the EURO-LABS facilities only once, while other users may have accessed them multiple times. However, for the purpose of this deliverable, we decided to count users benefiting from TA program only once, at the time of their first access. In other words, duplicates have been deleted.

For the given period, the total count of users benefiting from the TA program is 3557. After removing user who have accessed an RI more that once, the total count of users decreases to 2745. This means that 812 entries have been removed from the general count. While this may look like an important decrease, the charts presented down below show no significant deviation, whether the 812 entries are kept or not.

2.1.2 Geographical diversity

EURO-LABS offers Transnational Access to 42 facilities across 15 European countries, as distributed in Figure 1.

The distribution of the countries where the users' home institutions are based is shown in Figure 2.

The users represent a wide range of nationalities, with 85 countries represented, as shown in Figures 3.

EURO-LABS Facilities offering Transnational Access

Figure 1: Countries where EURO-LABS facilities are based

The efficiency of the communication and dissemination activities since the start of the project made possible to offer beamtime to scientists coming from institutes distributed over 54 countries and 1 IERO (International European Research Organization) – the only IERO being CERN.

Figure 2: Distribution of EURO-LABS users based on their home institute's country

Figure 3: Distribution of EURO-LABS users by nationality

The overall list of countries associated either with the user's home institute or nationality are divided into three categories depending on their official recognition, as listed below:

- EU Member State
- Associated Country to Horizon Europe (applicable for HORIZON-INFRA-2021-SERV-01 call, under which EURO-LABS is funded)
- Other, country that does not fit any of the aforementioned categories.

Figure 4: Percentage of users' home institute per country classification.

Figure 5: Percentage of users' nationality per country whether it is a EU or non EU beneficiary

Figure 4 shows that a large majority of people benefiting from the EURO-LABS TA program come from a EU Member State (71%), while the proportion of people coming from an Associated Country to Horizon Europe is rather low (4%). The same trend can be seen in Figure 5, with 67% of people are from a EU Member State and 5% of people are from an Associated Country to Horizon Europe (HE). Interestingly, EURO-LABS seems to be an appealing program also for communities outside of the EU. In particular, the percentage of people coming from other countries which are not associated to Horizon Europe is rather high (25% in Figure 4 and 28% in Figure 5). It is important to notice the high level of EURO-LABS facilities that also attract people from highly developed countries, such as US/Japan, that do not have facilities providing the same possibilities of the those in Europe. Moreover, by supporting users from developing countries, EURO-LABS offers an opportunity to work at frontier nuclear physics experiments and learn new techniques and approaches.

In addition, by focusing specifically on women, we notice that, among 740 women who benefited from the TA program in the given period, 546 of them - i.e. 74% - work in an institute located in a EU Member State.

2.1.3 Gender diversity

Figure 6 shows the gender distribution of the 2745 users who accessed a EURO-LABS facility in the given period. Men count for the majority (73%) and women for more than a quarter (27%) of represented users. Non-binaries are also represented in this figure.

Figure 6: Users' gender distribution

The ratio of women reported in P1 of EURO-LABS was below 25%, and clearly increased in the following period, with 28%.

Figure 7, split in two parts to provide a clearer distribution; it shows the number of men, women and non-binaries per country where the home institutes are based.

Figure 7: Number of men, women and non-binaries classified by the country where the home institute is based.

2.1.4 Age diversity

When it comes to the distribution of users by age, the data samples the 965 users who provided their date of birth, for which Figures 8 and 9 respectively show:

- The percentage of men and women by age group;
- The percentage of users working in a EU Member State by age group.

The present statistics corroborate the spirit of EURO-LABS, where the selection of students and young researchers was favoured in receiving TA support. It is considered that the contact with experiments at the early stage of their university studies or first steps in the research field will transmit the enthusiasm and expertise of the more experienced researchers and favour that they choose this field for their future development.

Figure 8: Percentage of men and women by age group.

Figure 9: Percentage of users working in a EU Member State by age group (when data is available).

Despite a few noticeable differences, the charts follow a similar trend in terms of age distribution across users. The highest concentration of users interested in EURO-LABS beamtime falls in the 21-25, 26-30 and 31-35 year-old range, which corroborates the fact that most of them are either young University students, PhDs or Post-docs. Thus the EURO-LABS project provides an opportunity for scientists/technicians to participate in facilities activities at an early-stage of their career.

3. CONCLUDING REMARKS

There exists many guides and reports on the inclusion of diversity in science, mostly concerned with gender balance issues as indicated above.

Most of these reports conclude on the relevance of communicating on a regular basis, about different issues of diversity:

1. Numbers resulting from monitoring
2. What is diversity and about people who make the diversity
3. Use of social networks, for wide broadcast and simple messages

In this document we report statistical analyses of EURO-LABS users, concerning their gender, nationality and age distributions.

It is essential to understand the mechanisms through which the strong representation of women at the undergraduate level—reaching 40% (see Figure 8)—diminishes across subsequent career stages. For example, the gender gap in the workforce often widens during and after maternity, contributing to this attrition.

The responsibility has to be shared: users in the majority groups who have more comfortable working conditions may more easily dedicate time to the improvement of diversity and inclusion in their surroundings, rather than their minority colleagues who struggle for their own inclusion.

The reports on diversity also point out the importance of raising awareness about, and counteracting, the unconscious biases that may arise at different stages of the scientists' careers (recruitment, promotion, responsibility...). This kind of communication needs to be strongly disseminated on a regular basis, to familiarize people on this very important issue. We believe that EURO-LABS is contributing positively to the above three points, thanks also to our dissemination activities, including social media.

REFERENCES

[1] Diversity Charter of APPEC, ECFA, NuPECC

https://nupecc.org/jenaa/docs/Diversity_Charter_of_APPEC_ECFA_NuPECC-9.pdf

[2] NuPECC Long Range Plan 2024 : Nuclear Science - People and Society, page 168

https://www.nupecc.org/lrp2024/Documents/nupecc_lrp2024.pdf

ANNEX 1: GLOSSARY

Acronym	Definition
APPEC	Astroparticle Physics European Consortium
ECFA	European Committee for Future accelerators
HE	Horizon Europe
HEP	High Energy Physics
IERO	International European Research Organization
NuPECC	Nuclear Physics European Collaboration Committee
RI	Research Infrastructure
TA, TNA	TransNational Access
WP	Work Package

ANNEX 2: LIST OF COUNTRIES OF USERS' HOME INSTITUTES

Algeria	Poland
Argentina	Portugal
Armenia	Romania
Australia	Saudi Arabia
Austria	Serbia
Belgium	Slovakia
Brazil	Slovenia
Bulgaria	South Africa
Canada	South Korea
China	Spain
Colombia	Sweden
Croatia	Switzerland
Czechia	Taiwan
Denmark	Thailand
Egypt	Tunisia
Finland	Türkiye
France	United Kingdom
Georgia	United States
Germany	
Greece	
Hungary	
Iceland	
IERO	
India	
Indonesia	
Iran	
Ireland	
Israel	
Italy	
Japan	
Latvia	
Lithuania	
Luxembourg	
Mexico	
Netherlands	
Norway	
Oman	

ANNEX 3: LIST OF COUNTRIES OF USERS' NATIONALITY

Albania	Hungary	South Africa
Algeria	Iceland	South Korea
Argentina	India	Spain
Armenia	Iran	Sri Lanka
Australia	Iraq	Sweden
Austria	Ireland	Switzerland
Bahrain	Israel	Syria
Bangladesh	Italy	Taiwan
Belarus	Japan	Thailand
Belgium	Jordan	Trinidad and Tobago
Benin	Kyrgyzstan	Tunisia
Bosnia and Herzegovina	Latvia	Türkiye
Brazil	Lebanon	Ukraine
Bulgaria	Lithuania	United Kingdom
Canada	Luxembourg	United States
Chile	Malaysia	Venezuela
China	Mexico	Vietnam
Colombia	Mongolia	Zambia
Croatia	Morocco	Zimbabwe
Cyprus	Netherlands	
Czechia	Norway	
Denmark	Oman	
Ecuador	Pakistan	
Egypt	Poland	
El Salvador	Portugal	
Finland	Republic of North Macedonia	
France	Romania	
Georgia	Russia	
Germany	Saudi Arabia	
Ghana	Serbia	
Greece	Singapore	
Guatemala	Slovakia	
Hong Kong	Slovenia	

ANNEX 4: COUNTRY CATEGORY

The country categories below apply to the situation as of 15 June 2022¹, i.e. the date of the EURO-LABS Grant Agreement signature.

Country	Category
Albania	Associated Country to HE
Algeria	Other
Argentina	Other
Armenia	Associated Country to HE
Australia	Other
Austria	EU Member State
Bahrain	Other
Bangladesh	Other
Belarus	Other
Belgium	EU Member State
Benin	Other
Bosnia and Herzegovina	Associated Country to HE
Brazil	Other
Bulgaria	EU Member State
Canada	Other
Chile	Other
China	Other
Colombia	Other
Croatia	EU Member State
Cyprus	EU Member State
Czechia	EU Member State
Denmark	EU Member State
Ecuador	Other
Egypt	Other
El Salvador	Other
Finland	EU Member State
France	EU Member State
Georgia	Associated Country to HE
Germany	EU Member State
Ghana	Other

¹ : [Association to Horizon Europe: State of Play](#)

Greece	EU Member State
Guatemala	Other
Hong Kong	Other
Hungary	EU Member State
Iceland	Associated Country to HE
India	Other
Iran	Other
Iraq	Other
Ireland	EU Member State
Israel	Associated Country to HE
Italy	EU Member State
Japan	Other
Jordan	Other
Kyrgyzstan	Other
Latvia	EU Member State
Lebanon	Other
Lithuania	EU Member State
Luxembourg	EU Member State
Malaysia	Other
Mexico	Other
Mongolia	Other
Morocco	Other
Netherlands	EU Member State
Norway	Associated Country to HE
Oman	Other
Pakistan	Other
Poland	EU Member State
Portugal	EU Member State
Republic of North Macedonia	Associated Country to HE
Romania	EU Member State
Russia	Other
Saudi Arabia	Other
Serbia	EU Member State
Singapore	Other
Slovakia	EU Member State
Slovenia	EU Member State
South Africa	Other
South Korea	Other

Spain	EU Member State
Sri Lanka	Other
Sweden	EU Member State
Switzerland	Other
Syria	Other
Taiwan	Other
Thailand	Other
Trinidad and Tobago	Other
Tunisia	Associated Country to HE
Türkiye	Associated Country to HE
Ukraine	Associated Country to HE
United Kingdom	Other
United States	Other
Venezuela	Other
Vietnam	Other
Zambia	Other
Zimbabwe	Other